

Beginning collaboration

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A reflective checklist on whether your proposal development and consortium are ready for multi-actor project work.

Benefits

This checklist of questions is a useful guide for reflection during your proposal development process to ensure that the necessary foundations are being laid for a true multi-actor project.

Practical recommendations

The reflective tool 'Beginning collaboration' was developed by the SHAPE-ID project as a checklist to be used at the beginning of the implementation of an interdisciplinary project. However, these questions are equally pertinent to consider when involved in the development of a proposal for a multi-actor project.

Reflecting on the questions of this checklist during the design stage of your multi-actor project has the potential to:

- ensure a common understanding amongst partners of the key elements of the multi-actor project proposal;
- showcase to a greater extent the co-ownership and responsibilities of tasks, results and outcomes in your proposal text;
- support in expectation management within the consortium.

Having already reflected upon these questions in the proposal development phase, gives your multi-actor project the potential to get off on a 'flying start' when it is granted!

Credit: The checklist was drafted by the SHAPE-ID project as part of the SHAPE-ID toolkit (<https://www.shapeidtoolkit.eu/>)

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

Recognize, and work with, the limitations of different organisations

Be comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results and outcomes

Balance needs of both yourself and the consortium as a whole

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[SHAPE-ID Reflective Tool - Beginning Collaboration](#)

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